

SPINUS

Spin based quantum computer and simulator

SPINUS project pursues a novel strategy for scalable solid-state quantum simulation and computation hardware based on nuclear spin networks and dipole-dipole entangled electron spin qubits. With a primary focus on scalability and overcoming the limitations of existing classical methods, SPINUS seeks to establish experimental platforms for quantum simulation (>50 quantum units) and quantum computation (>10 qubits), thus, developing an innovative quantum computer.

Social media

spinus-quantum.eu

@SPINUS Project

@SpinusEurope

Basic data

Project starting date: 1 January 2024

Project end date: 31 December 2027

Project duration: 48 months

Budget: 10 166 376.25 EUR

No. partners: 12 partners

Contacts

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